

1. Cultivation of *H. polymorpha* Yeast

The freeze-dried *H. polymorpha* also called *Pichia angusta* yeast stored in a glass ampoule was purchased from Leibniz-Institut DSMZ-Deutsche Sammlung von Mikroorganismen und Zellkulturen GmbH. The yeast was recovered by following procedure as per supplier instructions, illustrated below.

1. Remove the glass ampoule from the secondary packaging. Double vial preparation, sealed under vacuum:

2. Wear protective glasses when opening ampoules! Heat the tip of the ampoule in a flame.

3. Place two or three drops of water onto the hot tip to crack the glass.

4. Carefully strike off the glass tip with an appropriate tool (e.g. forceps).

5. Remove the insulation material with forceps and take out the inner vial.

6. Lift the cotton plug using a forceps, remove it, keep it under sterile conditions and flame the top of the inner vial.

7. Add 0.5 ml of medium specified for the strain in the individual strain entry (see above). Replace the plug and allow the pellet to rehydrate for up to 30 minutes.

Subsequent handling of anaerobic strains is described in our catalogue at > Culture Technology in a pdf-file and a video tutorial as well as in the specific strain entries. For all other strains proceed as follows.

8. Mix the content gently with an inoculation loop or with a Pasteur pipette. Transfer about half of the whole amount to a test tube with 5 ml of the recommended liquid medium, streak the other half onto a respective agar plate.
9. Incubate liquid and agar cultures under conditions specified for the strain.
10. Before discarding sterilize all the remains of the original ampoule.

2. Yeast preculture on solid medium

Solid medium was composed of (in g/L): yeast extract, malt extract, peptone, D-xylose, and agar-agar, which are tabulated below:

- Yeast extract	3 g/L
- Malt Extract	3 g/L
- Peptone	5 g/L
- D-xylose	10 g/L
- Agar-agar	20 g/L

100 ml test tubes and hydrophobic cotton (wrapped in gauze-mesh cloth) to cover the tubes were prepared. All the first four components (except agar-agar) were dissolved in 500 ml of double distilled water and the final volume make up to 1L. Then this solution pH adjusted to 7 using 1 N KOH. Thereafter, the solution was transferred to a big beaker and boiled. When the boiling starts the agar was dissolved in it under stirring or mixing conditions to prevent lump formation. Approximately 25 ml of this hot prepared medium were transferred to each 100ml test tube. The tubes containing the medium are allowed to cool at 45-degree angle so that, when the medium solidifies, a large area is available on which to inoculate the microorganism. Mouth of these tubes then covered with hydrophobic cotton wrapped in gauze and covered with filter paper, sealed with wire, and covered with aluminium foil to avoid contamination or water ingress into the tube during the sterilization process. These tubes sterilized in an autoclave for 20 minutes at 121°C.

3. Culture medium preparation

In order to use the conditioned solutions as a growth medium for the yeast *H. polymorpha*, in the fermentation process, it is necessary to provide a series of components that will complement the sugars of the solutions. According to Lindegren et al. (1958), these components are the following:

- Yeast extract	4.00 g/L
- Peptone	3.60 g/L
- (NH ₄) ₂ SO ₄	3.00 g/L
- Mg SO ₄ 7H ₂ O	2.05 g/L
- KH ₂ PO ₄	2.00 g/L

All the components were dissolved together in a distilled water with the final volume of 1L.

4. Yeast inoculation

Yeast inoculation is carried out in a Telsta laminar flow cabinet, mod. Micro-V, providing a sterile environment. Using a Pt loop, the microorganism is transferred in a zig-zag pattern to the solidified culture medium, on which it will grow, while it is kept in a culture oven at a temperature of 25°C. It is necessary to inoculate the yeast for its maintenance, in a fresh medium approximately every 2 weeks.

5. Preparation and start of the fermentation bioprocess

Prior to the day of the beginning of the fermentation process, the first operation to carry out is accelerating yeast growth. To do this, it is kept at 30 °C, in an incubator/culture oven, between 48 and 60 hours, prior to the start of the bioprocess. Before starting the fermentation, all the material to be sterilized in the autoclave is prepared, such as reactors, stirrers, Hoffman clamps, tubes to contain the samples, inoculum tubes and ultrapure water that can later be used to prepare acid solutions or base for pH adjustment during the process. All the apparatus to be

used for fermentation i.e., reactor vessels, the water circulation rubber tubes, the thermometer, pH meter and the magnetic stirrers were wrapped in large thick papers followed by aluminium wrapping were autoclaved at 121°C for 20 minutes.

Next, the components of the culture medium are weighed, for each volume of solutions to be fermented (500 ml). An additional volume of around 250 ml was also prepared to carry out the dilutions of the samples taken, dissolving the components of the medium, in ultrapure water. The medium components are dissolved in a little less than 500 ml of solutions, the pH is adjusted to 5.5 using 1 and 10 N KOH solutions, prepared with ultrapure sterile water.

Finally, it is made up to 500 ml with the conditioned fermentation solutions (broth). To introduce this medium, consisting of the fermentation solutions and the components of the Lindegren et al. (1958), in a sterile manner inside the already sterilized reactor, is filtered with a membrane using polycarbonate filter holders (also sterilized in an autoclave) using a peristaltic pump. Once the hydrolysates have been filtered in the laminar flow cabin, the inoculum developed for this purpose is prepared, dissolving the quantity of inoculum available in the culture medium. A calibration line between absorbance measured at 620 nm and dry biomass weight is used to determine the inoculum concentration (g/L).

When the necessary inoculum has been placed inside each reactor, the working temperature is set, and the stirring at 500 rpm, and the connections between the gums connecting the jacks of the reactors are made.

At this time the fermentation process begins. The sample is taken more often at the beginning, spaced as the process proceeds. In each sample we extract from each reactor, using a sterile syringe, 5 or 6 ml of suspension to determine the pH and biomass concentration. The sample is then centrifuged and kept frozen in the sterilised tubes prepared for this purpose, to determine sugars and ethanol.

6. Reactor (Languedoc Scientifique company) used for fermentation

